

DEVELOPMENT OF AAS INSTANCES AND REALIZING THE NETWORK / ASSET ORCHESTRATION

Deliverable D6.4

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Deliverable

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Executive Summary

TARGET-X focuses on integrating 5G in different verticals, use cases and defining new business models and scenarios relevant to the envisioned 5G and 6G. The Deliverable D6.4 provides the implementation of one of the key enablers for the integration of industrial devices and network domain. The outcomes of this deliverable justify the convergence of different domains in Industry 4.0 by representing digital twins of industrial assets in the form of Asset Administration Shell (AAS). This document introduces the 5G NW and 5G UE Asset Administration Shell (AAS) implementation details for TARGET-X. AAS will be used for network automation & orchestration and the potential vertical use cases to be studied in the project. This document has a particular focus on the development and integration details of AAS in TARGET-X.

In TARGET-X, AAS will be used as an enabler of vertical use cases as well as a framework to realize the automation leveraging interoperability. The concept of AAS is one of the key pillars for accelerating the digitalization of the processes in the industry and manufacturing. Having the AAS concept on a broader 5G deployment allows easier integration with 5G enabled devices that have their digital twins in AAS form. Although detailed designing AAS for assets is an important step in digitalization, product-grade implementation of the AAS is vital. Thus, implementation specific details of AAS need to be examined thoroughly.

From this aspect, understanding the different options to develop AAS and their advantages / disadvantages will have a great contribution to the community when it comes to productify the outcomes of the TARGET-X project.

In the previous deliverable [TAR23_D63], AAS design for both UE and 5G NW were provided. Some of these designs contain complex data structures that need to be developed in compliance with AAS best practices. This requires clear understanding of AAS development details.

Apart from development of respective AAS for both UEs and 5G NW, data sources to fill AAS submodel elements should also be investigated. For easy integration to the testbed environment, mock services need to be developed and used during the development of integration tools.

The purpose of this deliverable is to:

1. Develop the 5G AAS to represent the network infrastructure and its components;
2. Develop the UE AAS to model user equipment and its functionalities;
3. Investigate the relevant Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) necessary for populating the submodel elements;
4. Develop mock services to simulate the behavior of these APIs for testing purposes;
5. Build the active parts of the AAS that will fetch, parse, and feed the submodel elements with real-time data.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
CAPIF	Common API Framework
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DL	Downlink
DNN	Data Network Name
DT	Digital Twin
EPS	Evolved Packet System
EP5G	Ericsson Private 5G
GMLC	Gateway Mobile Location Centre
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
I4.0	Industry 4.0
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCS	Location Services

MCC	Mobile Country Code
MNC	Mobile Network Code
NF	Network Function
NSA	Non-standalone
NW	Network
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAM	Operations, Administration and Maintenance
OT	Operational Technology
PDU	Packet Data Unit
QoS	Quality of Service
RAMI4.0	Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSRQ	Reference Signal Received Quality
RTT	Round-Trip Time
SA	Standalone
SINR	Signal Interference to Noise Ratio
TS	Technical Specification
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UTDOA	Uplink Time Difference of Arrival
VNF	Virtual Network Function

1 Introduction

Smart industries require advanced communication technologies such as 5G and beyond networks. One of the main motivations for the development of 5G networks is to address critical requirements coming from the I4.0 use cases. These mainly focus on automation of network operations and configurations for efficient use of resources. However, this capability requires highly integrated environments in industries. Interaction between industrial assets and 5G NW has a vital importance. But, due to the complex security nature of 5G networks, interaction to the external applications is highly limited. Moreover, industrial devices are not designed to exploit 5G NW exposures by default. Considering these challenges, TARGET-X Project focuses on integrating 5G Networks in different verticals and use cases in smart industries. From this perspective, The Deliverable D6.4 provides the implementation of one of the key enablers for the integration of industrial devices and network domain. The outcomes of this deliverable justify the convergence of different domains in Industry 4.0 by representing digital twins of industrial assets in the form of Asset Administration Shell (AAS).

To have a common understanding across different value chains and solutions from various vendors, there is a need to have a standardized mechanism and concept for digital twinning. To establish interaction among all participants and enable end-to-end interoperability at the factory floor, one promising solution is Asset Administration Shell (AAS), which enables the digital twinning (DT) of the industrial assets. As proposed by Plattform Industrie 4.0, AAS principles are key to integrate physical assets (e.g., machines, products) into the digital world [AASDetails1].

Apart from deciding the digital twinning technology and designing the system accordingly, implementation, realization and integration of this technology have many challenges as well. This deliverable focuses on implementation, realization, and integration details of 5G NW AAS and 5G UE AAS. The implemented AAS and related components will be utilized in TARGET-X for integrating 5G enabled assets with the 5G NW. Additional to the AAS development details, the relevant data sources are also examined, and necessary services are developed, and details are provided.

1.1 Document structure

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 provides background related to the AAS design of the corresponding 5G components in TARGET-X. Section 3 presents AAS architecture options, AAS implementation methods, and best practices. Section 4 provides implementation details related to the 5G NW AAS and 5G UE AAS. In Section 5 Testbed integration details for the related 5G AAS are provided. Section 6 summarizes the deliverable and presents conclusions.

2 Background

This section provides a summary of the different activities reported in previous WP6 deliverables concerning the design and definition of the 5G AAS in TARGET-X. The description serves as the basis for the following sections, which will then define the AAS architecture and best practices for implementation, as well as the actual implementation of the different assets that form the 5G AAS, i.e., 5G network AAS and 5G UE AAS.

2.1 5G Network AAS Design

AAS plays an important role in integrating 5G into industrial domain to address the needs of industrial applications and OT processes, implementing an abstraction layer for the factory operators to manage the network based on their expectations. Depending on the complexity of the 5G system and the requirements, the 5G NW AAS can be standalone or composition of multiple AAS instances. The submodels in 5G NW AAS consist of both static and dynamic information. In addition to the information that does not change over time, such as network identity, the 5G NW AAS is expected to provide data that is updated based on the events and measurements generated by the network. The designed 5G NW AAS and related submodels are given in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1 5G NW AAS Design

The submodels and corresponding submodel elements are described as follows.

- **Network identification submodel:** This submodel is used to aggregate relevant information that describes the network and its attributes. Following is the list of submodel elements: List of DNNs (Data Network Name), supported frequency bands, supported frequency band combinations, attach type.
- **Network performance submodel:** This submodel will be populated by the performance data exposed by the network. Following submodel elements are stored in this submodel: Ratio of available cells, DL Delay in RAN, UL Delay in RAN, End-to-end delay for a network slice, DL RAN throughput, UL RAN Throughput, Downstream throughput at N3 interface,

Upstream throughput at N3 interface, DL packet transmission success on Uu, UL packet transmission success on Uu, RAN handover success rate, Timestamp.

- **Device connectivity performance submodel:** This submodel is responsible for keeping connectivity performance information of each device attached to the network. Following is the list of contained submodel elements: IMSI, Session ID, Ratio of available cells, DL Delay in RAN, UL Delay in RAN, End-to-end delay for a network slice, DL RAN throughput, UL RAN throughput, Downstream throughput at N3 interface, Upstream throughput at N3 interface, DL packet transmission success on Uu, UL packet transmission success on Uu, RAN handover success rate, QoS Status, Timestamp.
- **Positioning submodel:** This submodel keeps the positioning and its related information of the devices/UEs. Following submodel elements are contained: IMSI, Positioning technique, Geographic area type, Point list (conditional if P-SME2 is e.g., polygonal), Radius (conditional if P-SME2 is e.g., ellipsoid), Offset angle (conditional if P-SME2 is e.g., ellipsoid), Included angle (conditional if P-SME2 is e.g., ellipsoid), Timestamp, Estimated accuracy.
- **Dispersion analytics submodel:** This submodel is responsible for keeping statistical information and predictions related to the 5G NW. Following submodel elements are contained: Identifier, Time slot start, Duration of the time slot, Observed UE location, Application identifier, Data volume dispersed at the location, Data mobility classification, Data usage ranking of UE, Data usage percentile ranking of UE, Percentage of UEs in the group at the location, Predictions.
- **Device session management submodel:** This submodel keeps session information of UEs. Following information is stored in corresponding submodel elements: IMSI, Device Connected, IP address, List of Session IDs, Frequency band used by the device, QoS class of a session, Associated DNN for a session.

2.2 5G UE AAS Design

The 5G UE AAS describes the different functionalities, capabilities and performance KPIs directly related to the user equipment, that is, 5G devices. As described in D6.3 [TAR23-D63], in TARGET-X, the 5G UE has been treated as a different entity to the end device that is connected through a wired interface. In other words, the 5G UE AAS and the end device AAS will have individual connections to the 5G network AAS previously defined.

The UE AAS has been reworked to include more relevant information. The additional properties are partly coming from the activities of building an Industrial 5G Device Overview Database in 5G-ACIA.

The different elements forming the submodels slightly differ from those initially defined in D6.3, as some additional features were discovered/added throughout the actual implementation of such submodels. Changes have been marked with a *.

As done with the network part, the 5G UE AAS has been divided into the following submodels:

- **Equipment submodel:** refers to device specific data, such as model, manufacturer or power consumption.

- Elements: IMEI, Vendor, device model, Device Type, Physical dimensions*, Mounting options*, module, chipset, Chipset interfaces, transmission power (dBm), Internal Antennas*, External Antennas*, Operating Voltage*, Typical power consumption*, Operational Temperature, Interfaces (Ethernet, USB, ...), Ethernet Address*, Driver*, Firmware version*, SIM card slots*, eSIM support*
- **SIM submodel:** data related to the SIM card.
 - Elements: APN/DNN, IMSI, IP address, MCC*, MNC*.
- **QoS submodel:** refers to metrics for assessing network performance, such as throughput (data transfer rate performance) and latency (time it takes for a data packet to travel from source to destination).
 - Elements: RTT latency (ms), Throughput UL (Mbps), throughput DL (Mbps), maximum data UL (Mbps), maximum data DL (Mbps).
- **Positioning submodel:** directly related to the GNSS signal, essential for location awareness.
 - Elements: Latitude, longitude.
- **Radio submodel:** in this submodel, several parameters related to the type of 5G technology being used are measured.
 - Elements: RSRP (dBm), RSRQ (dBm), SINR (dB), technology (5G SA/NSA, LTE), cell ID, current 5G Band*, current LTE Band*.
- **Capabilities submodel:** capabilities for device configuration, supported bands of both 5G NSA and SA networks, support of various 5G features, 3GPP release info and diagnostics capabilities.
 - Elements: Device configuration options*, bridge mode support*, port forwarding* DHCP*, 5G NSA Bands*, 5G SA Bands*, LTE Bands*, 2G support, 3G support, MIMO support, 5G-SA support*, 3GPP release*, TSN support, RedCap support*, 5GLAN support, sidelink support, NTN support, slicing support*, Diagnostics SMC*, Layer 2 support*
- **Security options submodel*:** Firewall*, Password protection*, VPN Support*
- **Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment*:** based on the submodel template provided by IDTA [IDTA-DNP]

To further communicate contact information, e.g. for available support, optionally also the Submodel for Contact Information [IDTA-CI] can be implemented.

The submodels and their implementation details are further discussed in Section 4.2.

3 AAS Implementation Methods and Best Practices

Asset Administration Shell is highly adopted by smart industries. Many industrial device manufacturers are providing their devices' AAS bundled with the delivery. Although its usage is widespread across the industry, there can be found a very limited set of documentation and support. Especially, from implementation perspectives, it is very difficult to find a publication that discuss best practices in AAS implementation. In this section, we briefly provide our experience in AAS best practices that we find useful during the implementation phase of AAS.

3.1 AAS Architecture

Before going into detail in AAS implementation best practices, it is useful to understand AAS deployment architecture in TARGET-X testbed environment. AAS fundamentals and architecture related information can be found in [AASDetails_1]. In this section we will give a brief information related to AAS deployment architecture.

The basic setup that is planned to be used in TARGET-X project consists of an AAS Server, AAS Registry, 5G NW AAS and 5G UE AAS. For deployment, testbed environment that is set up in IPT premises will be utilized. AAS Server is deployed on IPT premises and hosts 5G NW AAS and 5G UE AAS. A typical basic architecture is shown in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 Basic AAS Architecture

In the adopted deployment architecture, AAS Server hosts all relevant shells. In our case, 5G NW and 5G UE AAS are onboarded into the AAS Server in IPT premises. To experience different development and onboarding methods, 5G UE AAS is developed using AAS Package Explorer UI, and onboarded to the AAS Server as an aasx file. On the other hand, 5G NW AAS is developed using BaSyx SDK and onboarded into the AAS Server using BaSyx libraries. AAS submodel elements' values are updated using AAS REST APIs.

3.2 AAS Best Practices

AAS provides multiple ways for implementation. An AAS can be developed in either:

1. **BaSyx SDK:** Eclipse BaSyx provides a rich set of open source SDKs for AAS development supporting various programming languages such as C#, C++ and Java. Developers can develop AAS passive and active parts as well as integration to the industrial communication protocols such as OPC UA, MQTT etc. The BaSyx communication middleware provides virtual End-to-End communication between any pair of connected devices. End-to-End communication is possible across networks, protocols, and vendors.
 - a. **Pros:** BaSyx SDK provides full flexibility for developers to develop AAS passive and active parts through built-in libraries. With the help of libraries AAS submodels and submodel elements can be manipulated within the application. Both AAS and industrial interfaces are easy to reach from the applications that use BaSyx SDK.
 - b. **Cons:** It should be noted that BaSyx libraries uses computational resources and when deployed for a multitude of devices, resource consumption can be a decisive factor.
2. **AAS Package Explorer:** Eclipse AASX Package Explorer and Server is a suite for viewing, creating, editing and hosting Industrie 4.0 Asset Administration Shell packages via graphical user interface. Eclipse AASX Package Explorer and Server suite accelerates the development of digital twin technologies based on standards such as the Asset Administration Shell and drives its adoption in the market.
 - a. **Pros:** Package explorer provides an easy way of AAS development that does not require any specific programming background. AAS submodels, submodel elements and their values can easily be defined and be exported to an AASX file format which is machine readable formatted file that is consumed by AAS Server.
 - b. **Cons:** AAS Package explorer does not provide capability to develop active part of AAS and any kind of interaction.
3. **HTTP REST API:** An empty AAS Server provides a rich set of REST API set out of the box, which can be used to manage AAS instances via REST API calls. One can create an AAS, its submodels, submodel elements via REST API, change submodel element values, modify the AAS design and can accomplish many other operations. This method requires knowledge of REST API usage, and development of a script that makes multiple REST API calls to the AAS Server to create required AAS instances.
 - a. **Pros:** Does not require programming knowledge other than REST API calls and scripting, and can be considered as a portable method.
 - b. **Cons:** Does not support development of AAS Active part unless active part is developed as a separate service exploiting these REST API exposures.

4 AAS Implementation

This section contains implementation details of 5G NW AAS and UE AAS that are described in D6.3 [TAR23-D63] in the form of AAS design. The implementation is focused on the future integration to IPT EP5G testbed environment. The 5G NW and 5G UE AAS design is shown in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1 Target-X AAS Design

4.1 5G Network AAS Implementation

In this section, we give a detailed description of the submodel elements that are collected from various APIs accordingly.

As applies to any industrial asset, the operations of 5G NW AAS highly depend on the exposures provided by the industrial 5G network to be represented. The submodels to be integrated into 5G NW AAS should be populated by the data and services exposed through the existing network interfaces. As AAS is an external consumer outside of the network domain, it is important to evaluate the applicability of the network interfaces.

Network exposures, by making network data and services available for enterprises (e.g., monitoring device connectivity, provisioning of network functions - NFs) through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), play an important role in driving innovation and integration of 5G capabilities into industries.

One of the main exposure capabilities introduced by 3GPP are implemented by the Network Exposure Function (NEF). Monitoring, provisioning, reporting, charging and many other capabilities of 5G system can be exposed to the external applications via NEF. By using APIs, such as Representational State Transfer (REST) APIs, the 5G services and capabilities are securely exposed to the external consumers. The northbound interface of NEF enables the authenticated consumers (i.e., Application Functions - AFs) to monitor the network (e.g., UE location, loss of connectivity), retrieve the analytics, configure the network, and execute other related procedures.

Another practical implementation of the simplified exposure interfaces and APIs is provided by CAMARA project, which is an open-source project within Linux Foundation to define, develop and test APIs. The CAMARA project conducts activities to implement APIs within the scope of, but not limited to, device, edge cloud and network [CAMARA].

In this deliverable, we made use of “Quality on Demand” API implemented by CAMARA. This family of API enables customers or vertical applications to be informed when network fails to meet QoS. Besides, it provides opportunity to set requested quality for a given traffic flow. We integrated the capability of storing “QoS class” of a given session by using the following endpoint provided by CAMARA: {apiRoot}/qod-provisioning/vwip/device-qos/{provisioningId}. Similarly, POST call for device-qos endpoint enables an application or vertical to define a new QoS class for a given flow. Therefore, based on the requirements communicated through inter-AAS messaging, 5G NW AAS can reconfigure the requested QoS for a session to enhance the performance and meet industrial requirements.

We followed subscription-based and polling-based data gathering services.

The subscription-based services, which are already defined by 3GPP, do not exist in the testbed environment. Hence, we manually implemented them to provide relevant information and put the information to the location specified by AAS (i.e., submodel element endpoint).

In this direction, we developed a service which generates events including the required information for the data that is requested by the AAS. This service produces data continuously, which are aligned with the 3GPP specifications. These values are generated iteratively in a random manner, according to a pre-defined set of allowed values.

In practice, AAS is expected to subscribe to a service provided by an NF by providing the API endpoint as the target URI/URL for the corresponding submodel element to be updated.

PUT calls are executed by the subscription-based data gathering service periodically, to update the submodel elements with the new values generated by the network. A similar approach is followed for other submodels as well, which expect data as if subscriptions are made.

The API endpoints to update each of this information and corresponding submodel elements are made available according to the standardized API specification provided by Plattform Industrie 4.0 [AASDetails_2].

In the polling-based data gathering from APIs, this is a used method in application development, enabling clients to retrieve updated information from servers at regular intervals. This technique typically involves utilizing HTTP methods, specifically GET and POST requests, to interact with RESTful APIs.

The polling interval can be configured based on the specific application requirements, allowing for a balance between responsiveness and network resource utilization.

For each of the submodels we have used the combination of these two techniques to fill the required data.

Furthermore, the details of the submodels, submodel elements, access methods and API path can be found in the appendix.

4.1.1 Network Identification Submodel

In the network identification submodel we are inserting/updating List of DNNs, Supported frequency bands, Supported frequency band combinations, attach type values at a specified API endpoint by sending a GET request with the appropriate data.

4.1.2 Network Performance Submodel

In the network performance submodel, Ratio of available cells, downlink (DL) delay in RAN, uplink (UL) delay in RAN, End-to-end delay for a network slice, DL RAN throughput, UL RAN throughput, Downstream throughput at N3 interface, Upstream throughput at N3 interface, DL packet transmission success rate, UL packet transmission success rate, RAN handover success rate, Timestamp values are inserted/updated to the dedicated submodel on the server using GET request.

4.1.3 Device Connectivity Performance Submodel

In this submodel, device connectivity submodel are filled with values of IMSI, Session ID, KPIs and measurements in network performance submodel, QoS status, Timestamp.

We interact with two different APIs to manage and retrieve Quality of Service (QoS) information based on a session ID. Initially, it constructs a URL to request QoS details associated with the provided session ID and sends a GET request to the first API. The response is parsed to extract the QoS profile value. Using this value, we then make a second GET request to another API to retrieve additional status information related to the QoS profile. The results from both API responses are encapsulated in a Result object, which holds the QoS profile and status values. Subsequently, it updates a submodel with the status value by sending a PUT request to a specified URL.

4.1.4 Positioning Submodel

The positioning submodel collects information of IMSI, the positioning technique, geographic area type, Point list, Radius, Offset angle, Included angle, Timestamp and Estimated accuracy. For this submodel in AAS, we utilized the services provided by 3GPP Location Management Function (LMF). The 3GPP standardized API endpoint implemented by GMLC (i.e., {apiRoot}/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location) is useful in retrieving the positioning information for a given device or a group of devices.

After sending a POST request to the aforementioned location service API, we can extract key location information like the positioning method, geographic shape, coordinates (longitude and latitude), horizontal accuracy, and timestamp. We send several PUT requests to update corresponding submodel elements in the AAS, reflecting the device's positioning data in real-time. The response contains location details like latitude, longitude, horizontal and vertical accuracy, and the method used for positioning. These values are parsed into a LocationData object. The aim is to effectively integrate external positioning data into a specified submodel in AAS for monitoring and management.

4.1.5 Dispersion Analytics Submodel

To insert all the necessary information for this submodel, we send requests to the APIs (i.e., {apiRoot}/nnwdaf-analyticsinfo/v1/analytics) to fetch data related to dispersion analytics. After receiving and parsing the JSON response, it extracts these values from the DisperInfos array and stores them in a list of DisperInfo objects. For example, DISPER_CLASS: Indicates the dispersion mobility class: fixed, camper, traveller upon set its usage threshold, and/or the top-heavy class upon set its percentile rating threshold. This value is only applicable to DISPERSION event. To collect

Identifier (IMSI or GPSI), Time slot start, Duration of the time slot, Observed UE location, Application identifier, Data volume dispersed at the location, Data mobility classification, Data usage ranking of UE, Data usage percentile ranking of UE, Percentage of UEs in the group at the location, Predictions, we send GET requests to update corresponding elements with the extracted values.

4.1.6 Device Session Management Submodel

To fill the device session management submodel, we need to collect the information for IMSI, Device connected, IP address, List of Session IDs, Frequency band used by the device, QoS class of a session and Associated DNN for a session by making a GET/POST request to an API endpoint using a specified organization name, site name, and IMSI (International Mobile Subscriber Identity). It parses the response to extract the info and encapsulating this information in a DeviceSession object. The responses from each GET/POST operation will be sent to this submodel.

4.2 5G UE AAS Implementation

The implementation of the 5G UE AAS is based on the architecture aforementioned described. In the particular case of the 5G modems developed by Fivecomm, there is no need to use an external computer that hosts the UE AAS. Instead, these modems are formed by a 5G HAT including the 5G module RG520N from Quectel (5G Release-16 compatible) and a Raspberry Pi 4 implementing OpenWRT, as Linux-based distribution for open management and control of the module.

In other words, the Python script that executes the code and creates the 5G UE AAS in the server runs on a Raspberry embedded on the device. More details about the device architecture can be found in [TAR23-D23] and also in the following Section 5: implementation.

Once the connection to the AAS server and the 5G modem is established, the Python script is launched. This script does the following:

1. Identification of the device that is connected to the host and recovery of its data. It gets the device information from the module by using different methods such as AT commands, *ping*, *speedtest* and others.
2. Gets information from the AAS template.
3. AAS definition and configuration.
4. Gets the submodels and saves the device info retrieved into submodel properties.
5. Creates the AAS in the server.
6. Uploads new AAS model information periodically, based on a variable called *Time*.

Note that the obtention of the different elements in *step 1* has been implemented by using separate Python functions, depending on the command or library used to get them. As an example, all elements obtained through the command `AT+QENG="servingcell"` are obtained in a single command inside a different function, in order to optimize computational time, as each AT petition takes time to execute.

All elements are first saved in a variable named *Device_Info*, which contains the information that later on will be saved into the submodels (*step 4*). Such information is obtained, at the time of writing this deliverable, as follows:

```
at_port=search_usb()
ethernet_interface = 'eth0'
if at_port == "null":
```



```

print("No configured 5G device found")
else:
    ser = serial.Serial(port=at_port, baudrate=115200)
    device_IMSI = get_imsi(ser)
    device_model = get_model(ser)
    device_serial_number = get_serial_number(ser)
    apn = get_apn(ser)
    dhcp = get_dhcp(ser)
    eth_address = get_ethernet_address(interface = ethernet_interface)
    #gps = get_coords()
    download, upload = run_speedtest()
    average_latency = average_ping()
    firmware_version = get_firmware_version(ser)
    servingcell_info = get_servingcell_info(ser)
    ip_address = get_ip_address()
    device_info = {
        'IMSI': device_IMSI,
        'IMEI': device_serial_number,
        'Band_5G_NR_NSA': '-',
        'APN': apn.strip(''),
        'DHCP': ",".join(dhcp),
        'Vendor': 'Fivecomm',
        'Device_model': '5G Broad',
        'Module': device_model,
        'Chipset': 'Qualcomm Snapdragon X62',
        'Chipset_interfaces': 'AT Commands',
        'Power_consumption': '2.8W',
        'USB_port': 'USB 3.0',
        'Ethernet_port': ethernet_interface,
        'Ethernet_address': eth_address,
        'Driver': 'Quectel wireless',
        'FirmwareVersion': firmware_version,
        'Max_Data_Uplink': '900 Mbps',
        'Max_Data_Downlink': '2.1 Gbps',
        'Latitude': gps['lat'],
        'Longitude': gps['lon'],
        'Throughput_Download': f"{download} Mbps",
        'Throughput_Upload': f"{upload} Mbps",
        'Latency': f"{average_latency} ms",
        'IP_address': ip_address
    }
    device_info.update(servingcell_info)

```

An example of the *Device_Info* data is shown below.

```

Device Info: {'IMSI': '999990000000101', 'IMEI': '866897040455224',
'Band_5G_NR_NSA': '-', 'APN': 'bronze', 'DHCP': '192.168.225.20, 192.168.225.60,
192.168.225.1', 'Vendor': 'Fivecomm', 'Device_model': '5G Broad', 'Module':
'RG500Q-EA', 'Chipset': 'Qualcomm Snapdragon X62', 'Chipset_interfaces': 'AT
Commands', 'Power_consumption': '2.8W', 'USB_port': 'USB 3.0', 'Ethernet_port':
'eth0', 'Ethernet_address': 'D8:3A:DD:3E:E9:5A', 'Driver': 'Quectel wireless',
'FirmwareVersion': 'RG500QEAAAR13A01M4G', 'Max_Data_Uplink': '900 Mbps',
'Max_Data_Downlink': '2.1 Gbps', 'Latitude': '39.477883188', 'Longitude': '-
0.338774541', 'Throughput_Download': '23.27 Mbps', 'Throughput_Upload': '12.17
Mbps', 'Latency': '24.356 ms', 'IP_address': '10.45.21.101', 'technology': 'NR5G-
SA', 'mcc': '999', 'mnc': '99', 'cell_id': '00042C009', 'band_5g_nr_sa': '40',
'rsrp': '-94dBm', 'rsrq': '-11dBm', 'sinr': '12dB', 'tx_power': '10dBm'}

```

As mentioned above, this data is later saved in organized submodels in *step 4*. For instance, the Equipment submodel information is saved as follows, for some of its elements:


```

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['IMEI']]['value'] = device_info['IMEI']

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['Vendor']]['value'] = device_info['Vendor']

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['Device_model']]['value'] = device_info['Device_model']

[...]

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['Ethernet_address']]['value'] = device_info['Ethernet_address']

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['Driver']]['value'] = device_info['Driver']

ue_submodels[submodelID['Equipment_submodel']]['submodelElements'][submodelPropertiesID['FirmwareVersion']]['value'] = device_info['FirmwareVersion']
    
```

In the following subsections, we describe in detail how the particular elements, as defined in section 2.2, are obtained. Note that additional elements in the different submodels have been included, which will be included in next phases of the 5G UE AAS implementation.

4.2.1 Equipment Submodel

EQUIPMENT ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
IMEI	<pre>cmd="AT+CGSN\r" ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") serial_num=[int(s) for s in msg.split()if s.isdigit()][0] return str(serial_num)</pre>	866355051215094
VENDOR	Constant value set by the device	Fivecomm
DEVICE MODEL	Constant value set by the device	5G BROAD
DEVICE TYPE	Constant value set by the device	Industrial Router / USB-Dongle / Ruggedized Smartphone / AR/VR / AGV / AMR / Module / Sensor / Other (Text)
PHYSICAL DIMENSIONS	Size (width x length x height) Weight	mm x mm x mm gram
MOUNTING OPTIONS	Constant value set by the device	None, Rack Mount, Wall Mount, Pole Mount,

		TH35 Rail Mount
MODULE	Constant value set by the device	RG520N-EU
CHIPSET	Constant value set by the device	Qualcomm Snapdragon X62
CHIPSET INTERFACES	Constant value set by the device	AT Commands
TX. POWER	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") cell_info = msg.split(',') if len(cell_info) >= 16: [...] tx_power = cell_info[15].strip() tx_power_dBm = str(int(tx_power)*10) return{ [...] 'tx_power': f"{tx_power_dBm}dBm" }</pre>	10 dBm
INTERNAL ANTENNAS*	Constant value set by the device	4
EXTERNAL ANTENNAS*	Constant value set by the device	6
OPERATING VOLTAGE	Constant values set by the device	5V
TYPICAL POWER CONSUMPTION	Constant value set by the device	2.8 W
OPERATIONAL TEMPERATURE	Constant value set by the device	Min, Max
INTERFACES	Collection, Constant values set by the device	Number of available interfaces
	Ethernet 100 Mbit/s	0
	Ethernet 1 Gbit/s	1
	USB 2.0	2
	USB 3.0	2
	Digital Inputs/ Outputs	0
	Analog Inputs/ Outputs	0

	Trigger Inputs/Outputs	0
ETHERNET ADDRESS*	<pre>result = subprocess.run(['ifconfig', interface], capture_output=True, text=True) for line in result.stdout.split('\n'): if 'HWaddr' in line: mac_address = line.split('HWaddr')[1].strip() return mac_address</pre>	E4:5F:01:96:89:E9
DRIVER*	Constant value set by the device	Quectel wireless
FIRMWARE VERSION*	<pre>cmd="AT+GMR\r" ser.write(cmd.encode()) time.sleep(1) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") fw=msg.split()[1] return fw</pre>	RG520NEUDER 03A02M4G
SIM CARD SLOTS*	Constant value set by the device Collection of SIM card type and number	Nano/Micro/Standard
ESIM SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No

*New elements not defined in D6.3

4.2.2 SIM submodel

SIM ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
IMSI	<pre>cmd="AT+CIMI\r" ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") imsi=[int(s) for s in msg.split() if s.isdigit()][0] return str(imsi)</pre>	999990000000007
APN/DNN	<pre>cmd="AT+CGDCONT?\r" ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") APN=msg.split(',')[2] # Extract the APN return APN</pre>	internet
IP ADDRESS	<pre>result = subprocess.run(['ifconfig'], stdout=subprocess.PIPE,stderr=subprocess.PIPE, text=True) match = re.search(r'wwan0_1\s+.*?inet addr: ([0-9]+\.[0-9]+\.[0-9]+\.[0-9]+)', result.stdout, re.DOTALL) return match.group(1)</pre>	10.45.21.101
MCC*	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] mcc = msg.split[4].strip() mcc = str(int(mcc)) [...] return mcc</pre>	999

MNC*	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] mnc = msg.split[5].strip() mnc = str(int(mnc)) [...] return mnc</pre>	99
-------------	--	----

The MCC and MNC have been moved from the radio submodel to the SIM submodel in comparison to the version in D6.3 [TAR-23-D63].

4.2.3 QoS submodel

QOS ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
RTT LATENCY	<pre>result = subprocess.run(['ping', '-c', str(count), host], capture_output=True, text=True) latencies = re.findall(r'time=(\d+\.\d+) ms', result.stdout) latencies = [float(latency) for latency in latencies[:10]] average_latency = sum(latencies) / len(latencies) return average_latency</pre>	15.3328 ms
UL THROUGHPUT*	<pre>result = subprocess.run(['speedtest-cli', '-- simple'], capture_output=True, text=True) upload_speed = re.search(r'Download: ([\d\.]+) Mbit/s', result.stdout) upload = float(download_speed.group(1)) return upload</pre>	10.25 Mbps
DL THROUGHPUT*	<pre>result = subprocess.run(['speedtest-cli', '-- simple'], capture_output=True, text=True) download_speed = re.search(r'Download: ([\d\.]+) Mbit/s', result.stdout) download = float(download_speed.group(1)) return download</pre>	38.68 Mbps
UL MAX. DATA	Constant value set in the device	900 Mbps
DL MAX. DATA	Constant value set in the device	2.1 Gbps

*The element defined in D6.3 as “throughput” has been divided into UL and DL throughput.

The throughput that is defined here, is the maximum throughput that can be allocated to the UE in the connected network. To obtain the value, the UE must run a speed test. The throughput values for the current traffic to and from the UE are not available at the UE. This can be obtained from the NW AAS, where the QoS values are available per PDU session in the Device Connectivity Performance Submodel (see Section 4.1.3).

In contrast to this, the MAX. data values are the maximum capability of the UE that is available from the datasheet.

4.2.4 Positioning submodel

POSITIONING ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
---------------------	------------------	---------

LATITUDE	<pre>#In bash: gpstmp=/tmp/gps.data gpspipe -w -n 40 >\$gpstmp"1"& cat \$gpstmp"1" grep -om1 "[^-]\?[[[:digit:]]\{1,3\}\. [[[:digit:]]\{9\}]" >\$gpstmp size=\$(stat -c%s \$gpstmp) if [\$size -gt 10]; then lat=`cat \$gpstmp sed -n -e 1p` fi rm \$gpstmp \$gpstmp"1" #In bash: [...]</pre>	39.477883188
LONGITUDE	<pre>lon=`cat \$gpstmp sed -n -e 2p` [...]</pre>	-0.338774541

4.2.5 Radio submodel

As mentioned before, all radio submodel elements are calculated in a single function by using the `AT+QENG="servingcell"` command. In the following table, we specify how each one of these elements can be calculated individually within this function.

RADIO ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
RSRP	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") cell_info = msg.split(',') if len(cell_info) >= 16: rsrp = cell_info[12].strip() return{ [...] 'rsrp': f"{rsrp}dBm" }</pre>	-92 dBm
RSRQ	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] rsrq = cell_info[13].strip() return{ [...] 'rsrq': f"{rsrq}dBm" }</pre>	-11 dBm
SINR	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] sinr = cell_info[14].strip() return{ [...] 'sinr': f"{sinr}dBm" }</pre>	19 dB
TECHNOLOGY	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] technology = msg.split[2].strip() [...] return technology</pre>	NR5G-SA
CELL ID	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] cell_id = cell_info[6].strip() [...] return cell_id</pre>	00042C009
CURRENT 5G BAND*	<pre>cmd='AT+QENG="servingcell"\r' [...] band_5g_nr_sa = cell_info[10].strip() [...]</pre>	78

CURRENT LTE BAND*	<pre> return band_5g_nr_sa cmd='AT+QENG="servicingell"\r' [...] band_5g_nr_sa = cell_info[10].strip() [...] return band_5g_nr_sa </pre>	40
--------------------------	---	----

*New elements not defined in D6.3

MCC, MNC have been moved to the SIM submodel in comparison to D6.3 [TAR23-D64].

RSRP, RSRQ and SNR can be modelled using the “ReceptionQualityIndicator” submodel element collection from the “Wireless Communication Submodel” [IDTA-WC]. The current value will then be obtained as described above. All other values from the submodel element collection are constant values set by the device.

Additionally, the properties current 5G band and current LTE band are added in comparison to D6.3 [TAR23-D63]. In comparison to the band lists in the capabilities submodel that lists the bands supported by the device in general, the bands in the radio submodel are the bands the device is currently connected to.

4.2.6 Capabilities submodel

CAPABILITIES ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
DEVICE CONFIGURATION*	Type of configuration for radio parameters and other features	Integrated Web Interface (HTTP) / Integrated Web Interface (HTTPS) / Cloud-based Management / AT-Commands
BRIDGE MODE SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes/No
PORT FORWARDING*	Constant value set by the device	Yes/No
DHCP*	<pre> cmd='AT+QMAP="LANIP"\r' ser.write(cmd.encode()) msg_byte=ser.read(ser.in_waiting) msg=msg_byte.decode("utf-8") lines = msg.splitlines() for line in lines: if '+QMAP: "LANIP"' in line: parts = line.split(",") ips = parts[1:] if len(ips) >= 3: return ips[:3] </pre>	
5G NSA BANDS*	Constant value set by the device	[78, ..., 257]

5G SA BANDS*	Constant value set by the device	[78,...]
LTE BANDS*	Constant value set by the device	[40, ...]
2G SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
3G SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
MIMO SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
5G-SA SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
3GPP RELEASE*	Constant value set by the device	Rel. 16
TSN SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /no
REDCAP SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
5GLAN SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
SIDELINK SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes / No
NTN SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes / No
SLICING SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	Yes /No
DIAGNOSTICS SMC*	Constant values set by the device SNMP Statistics Logs	Yes/No Yes/No Yes/No
LAYER 2 SUPPORT*	Constant values set by the device Support for Layer 2 Tunnel (GRE, vxlan) Support for Ethernet PDU sessions	None / GRE / VXLAN Yes / No

*New element not defined in D6.3.

4.2.7 Security options submodel*

The Security options submodel is new in comparison to the version in D6.3. While the focus of the UE AAS is on telecommunication settings and capabilities, we recommend capturing basic security functions to allow the users to quickly assess the available options.

SECURITY OPTIONS ELEMENT	COMMAND/FUNCTION	EXAMPLE
FIREWALL*	Constant value set by the device	Yes/No
PASSWORD PROTECTION*	Constant value set by the device	Yes/No
VPN SUPPORT*	Constant value set by the device	VPN type (IPSec / OpenVPN / IP-Passthrough / WireGuard / Other (Text))

4.2.8 Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment submodel*

In addition to the developed submodels, the 5G UE AAS should also implement the “Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment” submodel that is available as a submodel template at the IDTA.

It allows to provide information on the markings the devices is compliant to such as the CE Marking or IP rating. [IDTA-DNP]

All of the information relevant will be constant values set by the device.

5 Testbed Integration

The testbed for the AAS activities is the Fraunhofer IPT manufacturing testbed (for a more detailed testbed description and for understanding further capabilities, see e.g. [TAR23-D93]). There, a commercial 5G-SA system (EP5G) is available, that is used as the network for validation and serves as a data source for the AAS.

For integrating the AAS components, also the edge cloud provided at the testbed is used. In the Fraunhofer Edge Cloud, they are running on virtual machines (VMs) that host the online services of the setup.

In total, the following components are necessary to implement the 5G Network AAS and the 5G UE AAS:

- Basyx
- 5G-SA network (EP5G)
- Runner script
- Mock services
- Fivecomm UE

Figure 5-1: Implementation setup

In the following, the capabilities and functionalities of the setup are described:

Basyx is running in a Docker container on the edge-cloud provided by the testbed. It consists of the AAS server itself, where all the AAS are running, the registry, where the AAS are registered and the Basyx Web UI.

In the Basyx Web UI, it is possible to see the AAS that are registered in Basyx:

Figure 5-2: Screenshot of the Basyx WebUI

The 5G-SA network provides information about itself via a REST-API that is based on network exposure functions. We use it to fill the AAS submodel elements that are detailed in the appendix.

For the other fields, where the currently available systems do not yet provide the information, we have used static information and implemented mock-services for 3GPP and Camara APIs, specifically for TS29435, TS29564, TS29572, TS29520, Analytics exposure, SMF PDU and Camara Quality on demand.

The mock services are consumable via REST APIs. In section 4 it is described in more detail, how the information necessary for filling the AAS can be obtained. The functionality has to be available / implemented in the systems.

The information from the network is obtained from the 5G network’s API and the described the mock services. Java-based runners are obtaining the information and continuously updating the AAS on the AAS server. There are 2 runner services, the first one runs once to gather information from relevant 5G NW APIs. Update interval of this service can be configured using a suitable tool such as cron. The second service is used for subscription based 5G NW APIs and subscribe to the corresponding APIs. Data update periods for the subscription based services depend on the service type and can be configured within the subscription request.

The Fivecomm UE is used to implement the UE AAS in the testbed. The UE consists of a 5G HAT including the 5G module RG520N from Quectel (5G Release-16 compatible) and a Raspberry Pi 4 implementing the Linux distribution OpenWRT. On the Raspberry Pi, the Python script for updating the AAS is executed. First, it executes the AT commands described in detail in section 4.2 to obtain

the current values of the UE. Then, it updates the AAS via a HTTP command. The update interval can be chosen depending on the needs of the specific use case, we have implemented an update in the AAS every 1 minute.

6 Summary and conclusions

The Asset Administration Shell (AAS) is the standardized digital representation of an asset, the corner stone for the interoperability of Industrie 4.0 components organized in Industrie 4.0 systems. From the manufacturer's point of view the asset is a product. Since 5G Networks and 5G enabled devices are one of the key enablers for advanced digitalization in smart industries, digital representation of 5G related components for both 5G NW and 5G UEs in the form of AAS provides a flexible way of interaction between NW domain and IT/OT domains. This is a key enabler for network automation which can result in more efficient usage of resources and more intelligent manufacturing environments. With this deliverable, we have successfully demonstrated development and integration of 5G NW and 5G UE AAS and increased our technology readiness level by gained experience. From the WP6 main objectives' perspective; *to study, implement and benchmark different "beyond 5G" technology features on testbeds within the project*; the outcomes of the deliverable justifies the implementation and integration objectives. Going further, for the overall objectives of the project, the outcomes contribute to the project by enabling interaction between different assets in the use cases with the help of AAS standardized interfaces.

References

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[IDTA-WC]	Industrial Digital Twin Association e.V. (Hg.) (2024): IDTA 02022-1-0 Wireless Communication.

7 Appendix

5G NW AAS Submodels, submodel elements and relevant data sources

Submodel	Submodel Element	Access	Method	api path
Network identification	List of DNNS	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/nc/apn
	Supported frequency bands			Constant, manual entry
	Supported frequency band combinations			Constant, manual entry (IPT note: Hermes uses band 78)
	Attach type			Constant, manual entry
Network performance	Ratio of available cells	HARD CODED	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/pm
	DL delay in RAN	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/kpi/latency
	UL delay in RAN	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/kpi/latency
	End-to-end delay for a network slice	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29435_NSCF_InfoCollection.yaml (constant manual entry, slice1)
	DL RAN throughput	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/kpi/throughput
	UL RAN throughput	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/kpi/throughput
	Downstream throughput at N3 interface	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29564_Nupf_EventExposure.yaml
	Upstream throughput at N3 interface	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29564_Nupf_EventExposure.yaml
	DL packet transmission success rate	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/pm
	UL packet transmission success rate	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/pm
	RAN handover success rate	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/pm
Timestamp	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/kpi/latency	
Device connectivity	IMSI			Constant manual entry (imsi1)
	Session ID	SMF_PDU	POST	http://url:3004/nsmf-pdusession/v1/sm-contexts/:smContextRef/retrieve (constant manual entry, session1 for imsi1)
	KPIs and measurements	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29564_Nupf_EventExposure.yaml
	QoS status	Camara_Quality	GET	http://url:3005/quality-on-demand/vwip/sessions/:sessionId
Timestamp				
Positioning	IMSI	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	Constant manual entry (imsi1)
	Positioning technique	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Geographic area type	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Point list	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Radius	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Offset angle	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Included angle	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
	Timestamp	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location
Estimated accuracy	TS29572_NLMF_Location	POST	http://url:3006/nlmf-loc/v1/determine-location	
Dispersion analytics	Identifier (IMSI or GPSI)			constant manual entry
	Time slot start	AnalyticsExposure	POST	http://url:3001/3gpp-analytics/exposure/v1/a/ld/fetch
	Duration of the time slot	AnalyticsExposure	POST	http://url:3001/3gpp-analytics/exposure/v1/a/ld/fetch
	Observed UE location	29520_AnalyticsInfo	GET	http://url:3007/nmwdaf-analyticsinfo/v1/analytics
	Application identifier	29520_AnalyticsInfo	GET	http://url:3007/nmwdaf-analyticsinfo/v1/analytics
	Data volume dispersed at the location	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29520_Nmwdaf_EventsSubscription.yaml
	Data mobility classification	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29520_Nmwdaf_EventsSubscription.yaml
	Data usage ranking of UE	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29520_Nmwdaf_EventsSubscription.yaml
Data usage percentile ranking of UE	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29520_Nmwdaf_EventsSubscription.yaml	
Percentage of UEs in the group at the location	Subs		https://forge.3gpp.org/rep/all/5G_APIS/-/blob/REL-18/TS29520_Nmwdaf_EventsSubscription.yaml	
Predictions			Same as 32 to 41 with prediction flag TRUE	
Device session management	IMSI	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/nc/imsi
	Device connected	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/nc/imsi/:imsi
	IP address	EP5G	GET	http://url:3002/partner/v2/organization/:OrganizationName/site/:SiteName/nc/imsi/:imsi
	List of Session IDs	SMF_PDU	POST	http://url:3004/nsmf-pdusession/v1/sm-contexts/:smContextRef/retrieve
	Frequency band used by the device	UE_AAS		UE AAS Capabilities submodel
	QoS class of a session			
	Associated DNN for a session	SMF_PDU	POST	http://url:3004/nsmf-pdusession/v1/sm-contexts/:smContextRef/retrieve